

A Scientific Review on the Instrumental And Chemometric Analysis of Arson Residues

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Abstract: Arson is defined as any intentional or deliberate burning of property. This malicious intent is not only confined within the realms of destruction of property but also of destruction of evidences present at the scene of crime or to commit a crime. Hence, it is necessary to know - the cause of fire, identification and collection of evidences. Usually accelerants such as kerosene, diesel, etc. are used to set or accelerate the rate of burning. These liquids are used because they have low boiling points which will help in accelerating the rate of fire and thus, the main aim of arson analysis is - identification of accelerants in fire debris. Various analytical techniques are used for identification of accelerants such as GC, GC-MS/GC-FID. However, arson debris are a complex mixture and when these samples are analysed for the presence of potential volatile accelerants, interferences are produced with the additional compounds formed during pyrolysis or present within the substrate. This review concentrates and emphasizes on the advanced instrumental and chemometric approaches used for identification and analysing certain chemical compounds such as presence of aromatic and aliphatic components and many other ionic compounds in the residues for discriminating the interfering samples from the accelerants present in residues.

Keywords: Arson, fire, accelerant, chemometric analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Arson can be defined as any intentional or wilful causing of fire to cause destruction to life or property. It originates from an Anglo-French word meaning “the act of burning” [1]. Usually, such incidents are committed by the perpetrator at his/her convenience and much after proper planning. Moreover, before any official investigation takes place, the culprit has already left the scene of crime. In addition to it, due to the extensive amount of damage caused to the scene, it becomes difficult to prove the commission of crime [2]. Also from the safety point, the electricity supply is cut off and the arson scene becomes dark. Toxic fumes of partially burnt hydrocarbons pose an occupational hazard to the investigator. Embers smouldering under the debris are yet another hazard [3]. The main facet of arson investigation is the determinations of origin of fire i.e. the point at which the fire started [4]. Normally, a fire tends to move upward, and thus the origin is most likely to be located closest to the lowest point that shows the most intense characteristics of burning [2]. Generally, it has been found that when a fire burns in the upward direction, a V- shaped pattern is obtained on the wall. Also, charring of the wooden floors and spallation of plasters are a common finding at an arson crime scene. These characteristics are more profound near the point of origin [5].

While investigating an arson scene, three main points are looked into for – the place where the fire originated, how the fire started and who started the fire or in simple terms, who was the perpetrator. The first point is determined by a quick search of the scene. The investigator searches the scene with a view to locate the origination of fire. After the point of origin of fire has been located, the next step in the investigation process is identification of notable accelerants used to initiate burning or accelerate the rate of fire. Usually, in an arson scene because the fire caused is intentional in nature, accelerants such as petrol, diesel and kerosene, etc. are used to accelerate the rate of burning. Hence, the identification of accelerants in fire debris helps prove that it is an arson case. These samples are collected by the fire investigators from areas of suspected fire origin which generally comprises of partially burnt or completely burnt wood, carpet and carpet padding, curtains, etc. [6]. Also, it has been seen that carpet and carpet padding are often submitted to forensic science laboratories for the purpose of analysing residual accelerant in suspect arson cases [7]. The main aim of collecting these residues is that the accelerants which are used to set fire to the scene are flammable and volatile compounds which get readily absorbed or adsorbed on the surfaces on which it has been poured on or kept. Also, the accelerants are low boiling fuels which support combustion, thereby, accelerating the rate of fire [8].

The residues are collected by the investigators comprising of accelerant compounds in tightly packed metallic containers and sent to laboratories where they are subjected to a systemized process including of isolation or concentration, followed by detection and identification. Similar treatment is given to control or positive standards with respect to those of unknown and comparison samples. Various techniques have been employed for the extraction of possible accelerant compounds from the arson debris such as steam distillation, solvent extraction, head space technique and vapour concentration on charcoal. But for the identification of the possible accelerants in the fire debris instrumental techniques such as gas chromatography and GC coupled with mass spectroscopy is employed. This separation method is employed keeping in view the fact that the mixtures will get separated into their individual distillates and the organic components present in it thereby giving characteristic peaks forming a pattern such that it can be easily compared with the known standard [6]. Although for the detection purposes of the possible accelerant compounds other instrumental techniques are also being employed with a view to obtain the ‘fingerprint’ regions [9].

2. METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of the present review study, the researches carried out in the field of arson have been taken into consideration. For this study, those researches have been taken into account that shows the possible generation of additional substances and interference materials during the analysis of arson exhibits. Also, the use of instrumental techniques and chemometric approaches have been extensively reviewed.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It has been seen that the usually engaged techniques for the separation of volatile debris components are Gas Chromatography (GC), Mass Spectroscopy (MS) or a combination of both i.e. GC-MS. In addition to it, some other techniques are also employed for analysing the debris components procured from an arson scene such as flame-ionization gas chromatography (GC-FID) and this step is then followed up by comparing the resulting profiles obtained thereof with profiles obtained from the exemplars¹⁰. Moreover, in an arson case different types of exhibits can be procured from the scene of crime. The range of exhibits includes fingerprints, charred documents, partially burnt carpet and flooring materials, spalling of plasters among other things. The most frequently encountered form of evidence includes carpet and carpet padding materials, curtains, etc. which are submitted to laboratories with the view to determine the potential accelerants and analysis of the same in suspect arson cases. The arson samples during the analysis procedure results in formation of interferences with the notable accelerants for example, kerosene, gasoline, diesel, etc. because of formation of charred and pyrolysis products. The interference profiles thus obtained creates a problem in the qualitative analysis of the accelerant compounds [7]. Studies undertaken to test this theory has proved that the usual presence of petrol on carpets and padding materials does interferes with the possible determination of arson compounds. In addition to it, it has also been found that the profiles did show the presence of petrol but on closely analysing, it indicated the absence of petrol. Hence, in order to avoid these interferences, it becomes pertinent to study the comparative fractions of compounds either by studying the extracted ion chromatograms or total ion chromatograms [10].

The most common ignitable liquid (IL) that is used in cases of arson is gasoline. It is a petroleum product comprising of alkanes, alkylbenzenes and condensed aromatics. It has been seen that the ignitable liquids are usually fresh at the moment of fire but changes considerably during the course of fire. Certain conditions such as high temperature and presence of air results in the evaporation of the components. Moreover, because of the differences in the boiling points between the various compounds in a particular ignitable liquid, the degree of weathering is not consistent. If samples have not been collected shortly after the fire, they may also undergo bacterial degradation and this will pose a problem during the detection and identification of possible ignitable liquid [11].

Considering this theory of interferences and concentrating on the already done researches it becomes imperative to study in detail about the presence of specific chemical groups in the arson residues rather than only studying the complete profiles for the identification and detection of possible accelerant compounds. Researches done in this field have adopted different methods for recovering arson accelerants from fire debris for instance, distillation carried out by adding n-hexane and adsorption by activated charcoal. For the qualitative and quantitative analysis use of gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC/MS) is then carried out for utilizing specific mass ion programs. In addition to it, for initial examination of arson residues, heated headspace has also been used in conjunction with gas-liquid chromatography (GLC). Also, techniques such as solvent extraction, steam distillation, etc. has been used for the purpose of sample collection and which is then introduced into the gas chromatograph for the purpose of analysis. In addition to it, the readiness of wide capillary columns as compared to the narrow ones has made them readily applicable for the purpose accelerant analysis by GLC [12].

It is a well-known fact that forensic analysis of evidences collected from a fire debris site is extremely difficult analytical procedure because of the intricacy and variability of composition of sample. Study has been carried out for the application of comprehensive 2D gas chromatography coupled with mass spectroscopy (GC × GC-MS). This technique allows the linking of orthogonal retention mechanisms and consequently a high peak capacity. This study also demonstrated the current researches being coupled with the chemometric techniques for the purpose of reduction of data and selection of feature for evaluation of evidences from the forensic point of view i.e. regarding the questions arising for detection and classification of the ignitable liquids in debris samples obtained from a fire site. Chromatograms obtained were divided into two categories comprising of non-overlapping spatially delimited regions; wherein each of these regions a Local Ion Signature (LIS) was calculated by adding the intensities, per nominal mass/charge over all points contained within each region. This resulted in a decreased feature space demonstrating the original data as a set of consolidated ion traces. Consequent selection of feature selection was carried out by assessing the individual efficacy of each feature using a univariate score-based likelihood ratio (LR) approach for discriminating between pairs of same or different type samples. The retained features were then used to model each ILR class using linear discriminant analysis (LDA) [13].

The analysis of arson residues always have remained a matter of concern with the view to detecting presence of potential accelerants. A new technique has also been developed in addition to the GC-FID and GC-MS which is vapour-phase ultra-violet spectroscopy [14]. An arson case comprises the use of ignitable liquids for the initiation or acceleration of fire. The detection and identification of accelerants therefore forms a key feature to investigate an arson scene. It is known that the most widely used procedure for detecting and identifying the accelerants is GC-MS. But, before carrying out the chromatographic analysis, pre-concentration of the residues of ignitable liquids is necessitated. The typical process, ASTM E1412, comprises passive headspace concentration with activated charcoal strips for the isolation of ignitable liquid residues from fire debris and the residues are consequently desorbed from strips of carbon with solvents for example, CS₂. Worked carried out by some researchers, described a substitute to this technique grounded on HS-MS (headspace mass spectrometry). This technique is for the thermal desorption of the carbon strips and analysis of various ignitable liquid residues can be carried out by this procedure. Chemometric methods

comprising of cluster analysis and discriminant analysis were also coupled with this technique or applied to the total ion spectrum obtained from the MS for discriminating between samples being burnt according to the accelerant used. It was found that the newly developed technique of HS-MS is faster, safer, and more environmental friendly than the standard method [15]. Various techniques are being devised for the detection and identification of residual compounds in arson debris. One such technique involves the application of Raman spectroscopy. In a study, five polymer based samples comprising of carpet, nylon stockings, foam packaging, CD and DVD cases were burnt using each of the ignitable liquid sample consisting of petrol, diesel, kerosene and ethanol. Raman shifts were recorded and the change in Raman spectra helped in identifying the possible pyrolysis products as a result of burning. The change in spectra also helped in identifying the burned compounds even though different accelerants had been used and in spite of the fact that the chemical and structural identity of the samples got altered once it got burnt. The pyrolysis products identified the compounds chemical constituents of the burnt sample [16]. The main point which can be very well noted in all the researches done for the detection of potential accelerants in the arson residues is that, background additional components are still present from the arson residues in addition to the accelerants and the instrumental techniques used does help in their identification but does not tell about their exact quantity.

The use of chemometric analysis has emerged in the field of arson analysis and has proven to be a better tool. Although, work is still being done and this field is slowly emerging. Researches done in the field of chemometric does contain some challenging issues when it comes to analytical processing of the ignitable samples obtained from the arson scene in addition with the methods such as ASTM E-1618 which are quite effective. Some of the chemometric tools used for this purpose includes PLS-DA and SIMCA [11]. Few other studies have also used the techniques such as LDA, QDA and kNN methods in terms of the likelihood approaches in this field. However, it has also been found that the methods did not deteriorate the performance data results obtained for arson debris [17].

In yet another study done, diesel samples were examined using GC-MS and chemometric techniques to associate and discriminate samples for potential use in forensic and environmental applications. 21 samples were collected from 13 different brands. GC-MS data and mass-to-charge ratios were identified for aliphatic and aromatic compounds. The study also took into consideration the total ion chromatogram (TIC) and extracted ion chromatograms (EICs) of the chosen ions and evaluated by Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) and principal component analysis (PCA). Discrimination results obtained identified the chemical constituents which attributed to the fact as to why samples presented the most variance [18].

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